

Research Article

**Assessment of the Knowledge and Perception of Sex Education among School Adolescents studying in Marathwada region, Maharashtra, India:
A Cross-Sectional Study**

^{1*}Vishwas L. Patil and ²Amol T. Narhe-Deshmukh

¹National medical college and hospital, Sillod, Maharashtra, India

²Shivay Multispeciality hospital, Beed, Maharashtra, India

Article Info

***Corresponding author:**

National medical college and hospital, Sillod, Maharashtra, India

vishwapatil.1981@gmail.com

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Abstract

Implementing sex education in schools can provide several benefits to teens. Implementing sex education in schools empowers youngsters to make informed decisions in their lives. Research indicates that sex education reduces teen pregnancy rates, provides accurate information, and decreases HIV, AIDS, and STD infections among teenagers. Therefore, sex education promotes healthy teen sexuality. A cross sectional analysis was carried out to study students' perspectives on sexuality education in secondary schools. The analysis was conducted from December to March, 2023 among school-going adolescent adolescents in class 9-12th class in two private English-medium schools located in Urban area, but the participants are lived in urban as well as rural areas. opinion of participants and their parents about the receiving the sex education in school education. At the age of 15 the participants highly opted the Don't know 50 (12.5%), at age 16 higher opted were Yes (%), at the age 17 higher opted were Yes 104(26%) and at the age 18 higher option were Yes 105(26.25). The gender variable Males 240opted Yes 60% and females opted Yes 147 (36.75). Parents of participants Males were opted yes 390 (97.50) and 301(75.25) female opted yes. The age group 15-18 for choice for receiving sex education in school is good 296 (74), in terms of gender total 387 (96.75%) were chosen the sex education in school. As per residence total were 337 (84.25) and parents opted yes for sex education in school were 86.375%.

Keywords: sex education, secondary schools, Students, Knowledge and Perception

Introduction

Schools are key places for promoting sexual health and reproductive programs since they are one of the primary sources of sexual health information among young people [1]. School-based sex education interventions are integrated into the official curriculum and have the ability to teach young people how to make safe sexual decisions [2]. The implementation of sex education interventions may be difficult and multifaceted, with schools using various ways to delivering such interventions [3]. Adolescence is a period characterized by a range of physical, emotional, and psychological changes, representing a transitional phase from childhood to adulthood [4]. This stage of life is generally considered healthy, yet it can also be a time of complexity [5], serving as a bridge between childhood and adulthood. During adolescence, individuals typically experience the first signs of sexual maturation, which is often associated with a newfound sense of independence. Unfortunately, despite earlier sexual activity becoming increasingly common among adolescents, many are ill-prepared for this experience [5].

Although parents and families are primary sources of sexual health information, schools provide a supportive environment for students to learn and ask questions about sexual health topics [6]. Comprehensive sex education programs offered in schools cover topics such as anatomy, reproduction, contraception, and sexually transmitted infections. Evidence-based knowledge from such programs enables students to make informed decisions about their sexual health [7].

Sex education covers topics such as intimate relationships, sexual anatomy and physiology, sexually transmitted diseases, sexual activity and orientation, gender identity, birth control, and reproductive rights [8]. Indeed, sex education does not mean instructing adolescents in sexual techniques or acts, rather it entails giving the necessary facts, information or knowledge about sex and encouraging questions and discussions [23].

According to Obiunu [22], sex education helps in preparing adolescents to have responsible attitudes and behaviour towards sex for a harmonious sexual life. Its goal is to help students make wise, important, responsible and informed decisions by providing them with accurate, current and appropriate knowledge, with regard to their age, on human sexuality and the consequences of sexual activities. Sexuality education is also meant to help students develop a moral consciousness, respect for themselves and for others. It also helps students practice abstinence before marriage which stands as the best protection against sexually transmitted diseases and unwanted pregnancies among adolescents [21]. It is limited to reproductive health information which promotes abstinence-only to curb premarital sex and its consequences but information regarding safer sex and contraception are excluded because of the conservative social environment and lack of political will in Malaysia[9].

It is estimated that 21 million girls between the ages of 15-19 in developing countries become pregnant every year and 12 million give birth.[10] The World Health Organization states that one in twenty adolescents is projected to contract a STI per year.[11] Research has consistently demonstrated the effectiveness of school-based sex education programs in improving adolescents' knowledge, attitudes, and sexual behaviors [12-16].

So, in order to cope with the changes that occur throughout the teenage era, an adolescent needs be familiar with sex education. As a result, sex education is essential in teenage development.

The mixture of myths/ stigma secrecy, lack of knowledge, social disparity and negative media messages confuses young people and encourages poor self-esteem resulting in uninformed choices being made and it may lead to incorrect knowledge about sex, unprotected sex, unplanned pregnancy; Sexually Transmitted Infections-STI'S

including HIV/AIDS or deeply unhappy and damaging relationship [17].

Regarding the need of sex education among adolescents, it shows that majority of adolescents favour the sex education. A similar study was conducted by Jaideep K et al., in Chandigarh found that 95% of students were in favours of mainstreaming of sex education [18]. Another study done by Benzaken T et al., shows 90% favours sex education and study by Thakur HG et al., shows that 90% and 97% favours sex education, among boys 82.9% and among girls 75.6% respectively [19,20]. A study done by Dorle AS et al., from Karnataka found only 48% of student favours sex education in higher and senior secondary school and it was lower than our study it might be because of regional and cultural difference and also study was conducted five year back [21]. Implementing sex education in schools can provide several benefits to teens. Implementing sex education in schools empowers youngsters to make informed decisions in their lives. However, some argue that integrating sex education in schools increases the likelihood of sexual activity and is unproductive. Research indicates that sex education reduces teen pregnancy rates, provides accurate information, and decreases HIV, AIDS, and STD infections among teenagers. Therefore, sex education promotes healthy teen sexuality.

Highly successful sex education gives sexual health knowledge that is age and culturally appropriate. The information is supplied via creating a safe atmosphere for the participants. Such programs assist participants in clarifying their doubts and developing abilities in communication, resistance, and bargaining. Such programs also include medically precise information regarding contraceptive techniques, sexually transmitted illnesses, unplanned pregnancies, abstinence, and so forth. This education should uphold community values and address community needs. They employ interactive teaching approaches, which are executed by qualified educators. Therefore, new approaches are

required to further our understanding of school-based sex education interventions and how they promote positive sexual health behaviours.

Materials and Methods

A cross sectional analysis was carried out to study students' perspectives on sexuality education in secondary schools. The analysis was conducted from December to February 2022 among school-going adolescent adolescents in class 9-12th class in two private English-medium schools located in Urban area, but the participants are lived in urban as well as rural areas. The participants were recruited from a list of students that are currently enrolled in class 9-12th class. Participants were sampled based on age, gender, ethnicity, and study program to obtain comprehensive data. The study includes one-on-one interaction with participants, guided by questions based on current research results. The sample size was calculated as 400 (200 students from each school). The administrative departments of both schools were informed of the study's nature and asked for consent. The research included students whose parents provided written informed consent, whereas those who did not complete the questionnaire after two visits were excluded from study. We obtained ethical approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC) (ECA/215/11/2023). During the interview, participants were asked about their experience teaching sexuality education in secondary schools, their knowledge of reproductive physiology, Prevent the occurrence of sexual disease, their attitudes towards providing sexual health education in schools, and their opinions on the reasons and concepts for sex education, as well as a proforma on socio demographic information, were delivered to students via online media (WhatsApp, e-mail) who are not interested to face-to-face interview. Once the data was collected, the recordings were converted into a MS Excel format. The data was scored, coded, and entered into Microsoft Excel, data analysed with the statistical

programme SPSS version 20. The median knowledge and perception score was calculated. Chi-square test was used to find the association between categorical variables and expressed with 95% CI.

Result

Present study the participants are from 9th STD to 12th STD and also the participant’s parents in which age of 15 were 90 (22.5%), age group 16 were 80 (20%), age group 17 were 120

(30%) and age group 18 were 110 (27.5%). Student participants Gender of male were 240 (60%) and female were 160 (40%). The residences of students from urban area were 255 (63.75%) and from rural area were 145 (36.25%). The education of parents were illiterate 69 (17.25) whereas literate 331 (82.75%), in case of parents occupation labour work were 36 (9%), Govt. service 197 (49.25) and self employment 167 (41.75%).

Table 1. Sociodemographic of Participants and Parents

Variables		n=400	%	P Value
Age (Years)	15	90	22.5	<0.001
	16	80	20	
	17	120	30	
	18	110	27.5	
Gender	Male	240	60	<0.06
	Female	160	40	
Residence	Urban	255	63.75	<0.71
	Rural	145	36.25	
Parents education	Illiterate	69	17.25	<0.021
	Literate	331	82.75	
Parents Occupation	Labour work	36	9	<0.05
	Govt. Service	197	49.25	
	Self Employment	167	41.75	

In table 2 represents the opinion of participants and their parents about the receiving the sex education in school education. At the age of 15 the participants highly opted the Don’t know 50 (12.5%), at age 16 higher opted were Yes (%), at the age 17 higher opted were Yes 104(26%) and at the age 18 higher option were Yes 105(26.25). The gender variable Males 240opted Yes 60% and females opted Yes 147 (36.75). Parents of participants Males were opted yes 390 (97.50) and 301(75.25) female opted yes.

Table2: Participants and their parents’ choice for receiving sex education.

Variables		Sex education in School n=400			P Value
		Yes (%)	No (%)	Don’t know (%)	
Age (Years)	15	38 (9.5)	2 (0.5)	50 (12.5)	<0.001
	16	49 (12.25)	1(0.25)	30 (7.5)	
	17	104 (26)	1 (0.25)	15 (3.75)	
	18	105 (26.25)	0	5 (1.25)	
Gender	Male	240 (60)	0	0	
	Female	147 (36.75)	2 (0.5)	11 (2.75)	
Residence	Urban	218 (54.5)	1 (0.25)	36 (9)	
	Rural	119 (29.75)	5 (1.25)	21 (5.25)	
Parents of Participants	Male	390 (97.5)	2 (0.5)	8 (2)	
	Female	301 (75.25)	3 (0.75)	96 (24)	

Table 3 represents the knowledge and perception of sex education among the participants. At the age 15 the knowledge about sex poor in 68 (17%), at the age 17 were 55 (13.75), age 17 were good knowledge 70 (17.5%) and at the age group 18 were 100(25%). In gender variable the knowledge of sex is good in 200(50%) and in 115 (28.75) females. The perception of sex education in age group 15 and 16 were 70(17.5%), at age group 17 were 73 (18.25) and at age group were 110 (27.5%) and in gender wise males were 212(53%) whereas females 117 (29.25). Students from Urban were 145 (36.25%) and from rural were 97 (24.25%) observed.

Table 3: knowledge and perception of sex education among study participants n=400

Variables		knowledge		perception of sex education		P Value
		Good (%)	Poor (%)	Good (%)	Poor (%)	
Age (Years)	15	22 (5.5)	68 (17)	70 (17.5)	20 (5)	<0.001
	16	25 (6.25)	55 (13.75)	70 (17.5)	30 (7.5)	
	17	70 (17.5)	50 (12.5)	73 (18.25)	47 (11.75)	
	18	100 (25)	10 (2.5)	110 (27.5)	0	
Gender	Male	200 (50)	40 (10)	212 (53)	28 (7)	<0.06
	Female	115 (28.75)	45 (11.25)	117 (29.25)	43 (10.75)	
Residence	Urban	142 (35.5)	113 (28.25)	145 (36.25)	110 (27.5)	<0.05
	Rural	92 (23)	53 (13.25)	97 (24.25)	48 (12)	

From table no 2 observed that the age group 15-18 for choice for receiving sex education in school is good 296 (74), in terms of gender total 387 (96.75%) were chosen the sex education in school. As per residence total were 337 (84.25) and parents opted yes for sex education in school were 86.375%.

Discussion

The Participants agreed that their science-based knowledge on sex education was increased during secondary school. Participants proposed introducing blended learning through organized individual learning, conversations, and presentations. However, recall bias may have occurred in this study since participants struggled to recollect previously learned sex education themes from school. Sex education should begin in school

and progress to age-appropriate themes throughout high school.

Limitations: Despite its virtues, the current assessment has significant limitations that should be addressed. We cannot guarantee honest responses since sex education is such a sensitive topic. We were unsure if every student understood the questionnaire's questions and statements, given it was only administered in two private English medium schools.

Conclusion

The survey found that most participants (Students and their parents) had a positive understanding and opinion of sex education and thought it should be included in the school curriculum.

Participants recommend equipping educators with necessary abilities and utilizing diverse instructional resources. More research is needed among educators and parents to understand their perspectives on this problem. Teachers were the primary source of information on the issue, highlighting the importance of school in educating teenagers.

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Conflicts of interest

No existing or potential conflict of interest relevant to this article was reported.

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